

Photooxidation of *o*-phenylenediamine by singlet oxygen

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Abstract : Photooxidation of *o*-phenylenediamine by singlet oxygen has been carried out. After completion of photooxidation reaction, product was isolated and characterized by physical, chemical and spectral data. Effect of various factors like triplet energy of sensitizer, life time of singlet oxygen, light intensity and singlet oxygen scavengers on the yield of photoproduct was also observed. A tentative mechanism has been proposed involving singlet oxygen as an oxidizing species.

Keywords : Photooxidation, singlet oxygen, *o*-phenylenediamine.

Singlet oxygen, the excited state of molecular oxygen, is a reactive species. It can react with many compounds, like, pyrrole, histidine, fullerenes, bipyroles, thiourea, glucosazone etc.¹ Its reaction with these compounds results either in a chemical transformation or physical quenching of singlet oxygen. Some of the compounds can act both as physical as well as chemical quenchers. Physical quenching and chemical transformation in β -carotene, fullerene and phenols have already been reported².

Reaction of singlet oxygen with β -carotene results in β -carotene-5,8-endoperoxide³ while photooxidation of fullerene gives $C_{60}O^4$. In the photooxidation of phenol, *p*-benzoquinone was identified as the primary product⁵. Benzoic acid, phthalic acid, 1,4-naphthoquinone and a dimer were identified as the primary products during quenching of singlet oxygen by 1-hydroxynaphthalene, while in the reaction of singlet oxygen with 2-hydroxynaphthalene, phthalic acid and the dimer 2,2-dihydroxy-1,1-binaphthyl were identified as products⁶. *o*-Phenylenediamine used in dye industries being an electron rich compound, may be attacked by singlet oxygen which is electrophilic in nature, thus, quenching the reaction of *o*-phenylenediamine chemically. Physical quenching of *o*-phenylenediamine has been studied⁷ and the present work has been undertaken to investigate the reaction of *o*-phenylenediamine with singlet oxygen.

Results and discussion

The product is determined as $C_5H_5NO_2$ (m.p. 60 °C). Analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.) for $C_5H_5NO_2$: C, 54.84 (54.04); H, 4.25 (5.54); N, 12.20 (12.60); O, 28.71 (28.83).

IR spectrum of the product showed bands at 3400–2500,

1599, 1599, 1500, 1385, 1352, 1110, 1110, 1070 and 750 cm^{-1}

Following signals were observed in the NMR spectrum of the product. Acetone- d_6 (δ) : 2.04 (1H, singlet, -OH), 2.90 (1H doublet, -CH), 4.18 (1H double doublet, -CH=), 4.83 (1H doublet, -CH=), 4.97 (1H double doublet, -CH=) The product has been characterized as 2-nitrosocyclopenta-2,4-diene-1-ol on the basis of these data.

The above structure has also been confirmed by usual chemical test for nitroso group. Effect of various factors on the yield of photoproduct was also studied.

The dependence of the percentage yield of the product on the triplet energies of various sensitizers has also been studied. The effect of sensitizers on the yield of photoproduct is reported in Table 1.

Table 1. Effect of triplet energy of sensitizer

Sensitizer	Triplet energy (kcal mol ⁻¹)	Yield (%)
Methylene blue	34.0	6.8 ± 0.2
Rose bengal	37.5–42.2	2.8 ± 0.1
Eosin	43.2–46.0	2.4 ± 0.1
Fluorescein	45.2–48.1	0.5 ± 0.05

It was observed that as the triplet energy of the sensitizer was increased, the yield of the photoproduct decreases.

All these triplet energies are sufficient for the formation of singlet oxygen $^1\text{O}_2$ ($^1\Delta_g$) (energy is $22.5 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$) but rose bengal, eosin and fluorescein have enough triplet energy for the transfer to form the singlet oxygen $^1\text{O}_2$ ($^1\Sigma_g^+$) (energy is $37.35 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$). The energy difference in triplet state of the dye and singlet state of molecular oxygen is in the order : fluorescein > eosin > rose bengal > methylene blue.

As the difference in these two states increases, there is less possibility of formation of singlet oxygen ($^1\Delta_g$), which is responsible for the oxidation and as a consequence, the yield decreases. The life time of sigma singlet oxygen is 10^{-9} s in liquid phase whereas of delta oxygen is 10^{-3} s, so sigma singlet oxygen is rapidly quenched in solution and, therefore $^1\text{O}_2$ ($^1\Delta_g$) may be considered responsible for the oxidation.

Photooxygenation was also carried out in the presence of different light intensities, using methylene blue as a sensitizer. The effect of light intensities on the yield of photoproduct is reported in Table 2.

Table 2. Effect of light intensity

Irradiation time = 24 h, [sensitizer] = $1.0 \times 10^{-5} \text{ M}$	
Light intensity (mW cm^{-2})	Yield (%)
30.0	5.5 ± 0.2
43.0	6.8 ± 0.2
50.0	7.2 ± 0.2
60.0	9.9 ± 0.3

It has been observed that the yield of the product increases as the intensity of light was increased. This may be attributed to the fact that on increasing the light intensity, number of excited dye molecules will also increase. Therefore, more singlet oxygen molecules will be generated and as a consequence, the yield of the product also increases.

The effect of nature of solvent on the photooxidation of *o*-phenylenediamine was observed using different solvents. Yield of the product in different solvents have been determined. Results are reported in Table 3.

Table 3. Effect of nature of solvent

Solvent	Life time of singlet oxygen	Yield (%)
	(μs)	
Methanol	8.5	5.6 ± 0.2
Ethanol	12.0	6.8 ± 0.2
Acetone	26.0	12.7 ± 0.3
Ethyl acetate	47 ± 15	29.9 ± 0.4

The yield was higher in non-polar or partially polar solvents. The yield was found to increase as the polarity of the solvent decreases. This may be attributed to the longer life

time of singlet oxygen in partial polar or non-polar solvents, which will provide the singlet oxygen enough time to react with *o*-phenylenediamine.

Dye-sensitized photooxygenation of *o*-phenylenediamine has also been carried out in presence of various singlet oxygen scavengers like DABCO and CoCl_2 . It was observed that reaction almost stopped in presence of singlet oxygen scavengers. It confirms the participation of singlet oxygen as an active oxidizing species in this reaction.

Mechanism : From above data, a tentative mechanism for this reaction has been proposed as :

Step I : Generation of singlet oxygen :

Step II : Reaction of singlet oxygen with *o*-phenylenediamine :

The first step of the reaction is the excitation of dye molecule to its first excited state, which undergoes intersystem crossing (ISC) to give its corresponding triplet state. This triplet state reacts further with ground state of oxygen ($^3\text{O}_2$) to generate singlet oxygen.

In second step, this singlet oxygen attacks on amino group of *o*-phenylenediamine giving *o*-nitrosoaniline. Now another molecule of singlet oxygen attacks *o*-nitrosoaniline to form a dioxetane. This dioxetane degrades to give a molecule containing a carbonyl and an amide group. Now this compound changes into product through decarboxylation, deamination and ultimately cyclization occurs.

Experimental

0.5 g of the *o*-phenylenediamine was dissolved in 50.0 mL of ethanol. A few mL solution of sensitizer was added to this solution so that the concentration of sensitizer in the reaction mixture was $1.0 \times 10^{-5} \text{ M}$. The solution was then irradiated with a light source. The light intensity was kept at 40.0 mW cm^{-2} . A water filter was used to avoid infrared radiations. The air was continuously bubbled in the reaction mixture by an aerator.

Note

The progress of reaction was observed with the help of thin layer chromatography at regular time intervals. Solvent system employed for thin layer chromatography was benzene : ether (1 : 3). After 18 h of irradiation, tlc plate showed two spots; one yellow ($R_f = 0.92$) corresponding to substrate (*o*-phenylenediamine) and another orange-red ($R_f = 0.61$) corresponding to product. After 24 h irradiation, the reaction was stopped, and solution was decolorized. The product from decolorized solution was isolated by preparative tlc.

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